

Strategies for the Success of Leaders in Managing Non-Formal Schools in Remote Areas in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

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This study examines the Leader's success in managing the Nurul Huda Quran Education Park (TPQ) in Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village, Maluku Tengah Regency in facing various challenges faced by educational institutions in disadvantaged areas. The research method used in this study is a case study research method. The study's results found that TPQ Nurul Huda successfully created a collaborative and innovative environment through a participatory leadership style, which supports improving the quality of teaching and strengthening relationships with the local community. Utilizing local resources, including human resources, infrastructure, and local wisdom, is the primary key to overcoming existing limitations. Indicators of the success of TPQ Nurul Huda can be seen in the increasing quality of education, active community participation, and long-term impacts on students. The strategies implemented by TPQ leaders show that with a clear vision and inclusive leadership, non-formal educational institutions in disadvantaged areas can achieve significant success. This study emphasizes the importance of community-based leadership and utilization of local resources in creating quality education that positively impacts society.

KEYWORDS:

Strategy, Leadership, Success, Remote Area

1. INTRODUCTION

The Qur'an Education Park (TPQ) is a non-formal educational institution that focuses on Islamic religious education. Its main aim is to provide Al-Qur'an teaching and form a generation that loves and uses the Qur'an as a guide to life. In Islamic education, TPQ has a vital role in teaching religious knowledge and forming good character and behavior. Teaching the Koran at TPQ, especially in reading it well and correctly, including recitation, is a necessary foundation that must be instilled from an early age (Khamidah & Maunah, 2023; Rifkah Dewi et al., 2023).

The Al-Qur'an Education Park (TPQ) plays a vital role in forming a Qur'anic generation who understands and can read the Al-Qur'an and applies Islamic values in everyday life. TPQ is a non-formal education center that focuses on teaching the Koran and developing morals for children from an early age. The success of TPQ depends on how this institution is managed, especially by its leaders. Effective

leadership is critical in ensuring TPQ can achieve its goals, even though it often faces various challenges, such as limited resources, infrastructure, and community support (Nugraheni, 2023).

TPQ leaders have complex responsibilities, from ensuring the quality of teaching and managing human resources to building strong relationships with the community and students' parents. The success of leaders in managing TPQ is not only visible from the increasing number of students or satisfactory learning outcomes but also from how this institution is able to adapt to the local context and face existing challenges (Qomar, 2018).

In many incredibly underdeveloped areas or with limited access to adequate formal education facilities, TPQ is essential in providing affordable and quality religious education. However, the success of TPQ in these areas often depends on the initiatives and strategies taken by institutional leaders. Leaders who can utilize local resources, build collaboration with community leaders, and continue innovating teaching methods will find it easier to bring TPQ to success (Nurdin et al., 2021).

Success in managing TPQ also includes the leader's ability to create a conducive learning environment where students feel comfortable and motivated to learn. In addition, the ability to develop and maintain high teaching standards and integrate

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technology into the educational process is an important aspect of measuring leadership success at TPQ.

In Maluku Tengah Regency, one of the underdeveloped areas in Maluku Province, there is TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village, which has played a significant role in forming the Qur'ani generation. Established in the 2000s, TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village has not only survived but has also experienced rapid development (Sugi, 2023). This can be seen from the number of students, which has almost reached 500 and is supported by a teaching board consisting of 20 people. TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village has now developed by adding Early Childhood Education (PAUD) to its educational institutions.

The success of TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village in managing its institutions, especially in areas with limitations such as Maluku Tengah Regency, cannot be separated from effective leadership patterns. TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village leaders have overcome various challenges, both in terms of resources and in creating a supportive learning environment for students. The leadership pattern implemented has proven successful in attracting public interest and improving the quality of education offered.

This research focuses on TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village in Maluku Tengah Regency to explore how the leadership patterns implemented have contributed to the success and development of this institution. Through this research, it is hoped that a deeper understanding can be gained regarding the role of leadership in managing TPQ and how this can be applied to improve the quality of Islamic education in other underdeveloped areas.

II. METHOD

This study is about the pattern and success of leaders in managing the Nurul Huda Al-Qur'an Education Park (TPQ) in Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village, in a remote area such as Maluku Tengah Regency. The research method used is a qualitative case study approach. The case study approach allows researchers to explore in depth how leadership patterns are applied, how leaders manage existing challenges, and how various stakeholders, including teachers, students, parents, and the surrounding community, view the success of this management (Hutchings et al., 2018).

Case studies are an in-depth qualitative approach that aims to understand a phenomenon in a specific context. This research will use TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village in Maluku Tengah Regency as a "case" for analysis. It will explore various aspects of TPQ management, including leadership patterns, management strategies, challenges faced, and success factors specific to this TPQ (Kalua, 2023).

Expert opinion: Yin (2013), in his book *Case Study Research: Design and Methods*, states that case studies are efficient for research that wants to understand unique and complex

contexts. In this case study, researchers were able to study leadership patterns in detail and gain a holistic understanding of how TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village leaders succeeded in overcoming challenges in underdeveloped areas (Yin, 2013).

This research uses data collection techniques in the form of in-depth interviews. In-depth interviews with TPQ leaders, teachers, parents, and community figures will provide rich insight into the leadership patterns implemented, challenges faced, and perceptions of TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village 's success. (Flinders,1997), in *InterViews: An Introduction to Qualitative Research Interviewing*, states that in-depth interviews allow researchers to obtain wealthy and detailed information about the subject under study, especially in understanding the respondents' personal experiences and in-depth views (Flinders, 1997).

Researchers also use participatory observation to be directly involved in TPQ activities to observe how leadership is carried out, how interactions between leaders, teachers, and students occur, and how the community is engaged in TPQ activities. According to Seim (2024) in *Participant Observation*, participant observation provides researchers with a direct understanding of the social environment and individual behavior in their natural context (Seim, 2024). It is beneficial for qualitative research that focuses on social processes. Documents such as TPQ annual reports, meeting notes, and work programs can be analyzed to understand the organizational structure, policies, and management strategies implemented. Bowen (2009), in *Document Analysis as a Qualitative Research Method*, states that document analysis is a beneficial technique in qualitative research to obtain contextual and historical data relevant to the research subject (Bowen, 2009).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The pattern of leadership success in managing the Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village Qur'an Education Park (TPQ) in Maluku Tengah Regency can be explained through the various approaches and strategies implemented by the institution's leaders. This success did not occur by chance but resulted from combining management skills, a deep understanding of the local context, and a solid commitment to the institution's vision and mission.

The leader of TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village has a clear vision to make TPQ a superior educational institution that will form the Qur'anic generation in Maluku Tengah Regency. This vision focuses on long-term achievements, namely creating an academic environment that produces children who can read the Koran well and behave according to Islamic teachings. The institution's mission, which includes teaching the Koran and forming an Islamic character, is implemented consistently through various educational programs and religious activities. Consistency in

carrying out this mission ensures that all TPQ activities are aligned with the institution's main objectives. Elice, an expert in Islamic education management, states, "A strong vision provides clear direction and goals for an educational institution, while a well-implemented mission ensures that the vision can be achieved through concrete daily actions." In the context of TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village, this vision and mission are translated into consistent educational programs that focus on building Qur'anic character (Elice & Semin, 2023).

Participative Leadership

TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village TPQ leaders apply a participative leadership style in which all parties involved in TPQ, including teachers, staff, students, and parents, are invited to contribute to decision-making. This creates a sense of shared ownership and responsibility, which in turn strengthens the commitment of all parties to the institution's success.

A participative leadership style involves team members or subordinates in the decision-making process. This includes listening to ideas, input, and opinions from all members of the organization before making a final decision. According to Avolio and Bass, participative leadership not only increases staff involvement but also increases their commitment and responsibility for the decisions made. This style is particularly relevant in non-formal educational contexts such as TPQ, where collaboration and active participation are critical to the institution's success (Salter et al., 2014).

TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village in Maluku Tengah Regency has implemented a participative leadership style as one of the main strategies for managing the institution. These TPQ leaders involve the teaching board, administrative staff, and the local community in planning and decision-making. This creates a strong sense of ownership among all stakeholders and improves the institution's operational effectiveness. According to research by Yukl (2013), a participative leadership style is very effective in creating a positive work climate and increasing team motivation and performance (Yukl, 2013).

The participative leadership style applied at TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village has several significant positive impacts:

1. **Increased Engagement and Job Satisfaction:** Participatory leadership involves teachers and staff in decision-making, increasing their sense of ownership and responsibility for the results achieved. Robbins and Judge (2017) show that participation in decision-making increases job satisfaction and reduces staff turnover rates (Robbins & Judge, 2017).
2. **Increased Innovation and Creativity:** Through active participation in decision-making, team members feel free to implement new ideas and creative solutions to the institution's challenges. A participative leadership style also encourages a work environment that

supports innovation, which is very important in facing operational difficulties in underdeveloped areas. According to research by Hackman and Wageman (2005), greater decision-making involvement is directly related to increased organizational innovation (Hackman & Wageman, 2005).

3. **Building Trust and Collaboration:** Participative leadership helps build trust between leaders, staff, and team members. This trust is important for creating a harmonious and collaborative work environment where all members feel valued and heard. This is in accordance with the findings of Goleman et al. (2002), who emphasize that trust is fundamental to leadership effectiveness and team success (Goleman et al., 2002).

Even though it has many advantages, implementing a participative leadership style also faces challenges. One of the main challenges is the potential for a longer decision-making time because this process involves many parties. In some situations, leaders may encounter resistance from members unfamiliar with participative approaches or feel uncomfortable being involved in the decision-making process. However, with training and effective communication, these challenges can be overcome.

A recent study by Lee, Willis, and Tian (2018) confirmed that participative leadership positively impacts team performance and organizational success, especially in educational contexts. The study also found participative leadership is particularly effective in mission-oriented organizations, such as TPQ, whose primary goal is to provide significant social and educational impact. In the context of TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village, implementing a participative leadership style not only improves the institution's internal performance but also strengthens relationships with the local community, which is one of the critical factors in the institution's success (Lee et al., 2018).

The participatory leadership style applied by the leaders of TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village in Maluku Tengah Regency has proven to be one of the keys to the success of this institution. TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village leaders succeeded in creating a collaborative, innovative, and solution-oriented environment by involving staff, teachers, and the community in the decision-making process. This aligns with modern leadership theories emphasizing the importance of participation and involvement in achieving organizational success. Despite facing several challenges, the benefits of this leadership style are visible in improving the quality of education and community engagement, which ultimately contributes to the success and sustainability of TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village.

Success Indicators

Indicators of success in managing the Maluku Tengah Regency Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village

Qur'an Education Park (TPQ) can be seen from various aspects, which include the quality of education, community participation, resource management, and long-term impact on students. The following is a more detailed explanation of these indicators:

1. **Quality of Teaching and Learning:** One of the leading indicators of TPQ success is students' ability to read the Al-Qur'an with correct recitation. According to Azyumardi Azra, an Islamic education expert, "Students' ability to read the Koran with correct recitation is the foundation of Qur'anic education. The success of TPQ can be measured by how well the institution can form this basic ability in its students." The success of TPQ can also be seen in how well students can complete the established curriculum. A curriculum that includes teaching recitation, memorizing verses of the Koran, and understanding the basics of the Islamic religion are essential indicators. If students consistently progress in this curriculum, the TPQ can be considered successful (Marhamah & Abdullah, 2020).
2. **Number and Involvement of Students:** An increase in students each year indicates success. Zainal Arifin, stated, "The growth in the number of students shows public confidence in the quality of education provided by TPQ. This also reflects the effectiveness of leadership in managing and promoting the institution." Success can also be measured from student involvement in various TPQ activities. Active participation in class, consistent attendance, and involvement in extracurricular activities such as competitions or religious events are important indicators of success in creating an engaging and effective learning environment (Arifin, 2019).
3. **Community Participation and Support:** The success of TPQ can be seen from the level of support provided by the local community. This may include financial support, material donations, or involvement in TPQ activities. According to Abd. Rahman Mas'ud, "The level of local community participation and support is the main indicator of the success of a non-formal Islamic education institution. This support shows that the community sees TPQ as an important and relevant institution." Parents actively involved in their children's educational process at TPQ, such as by attending parent meetings, helping supervise learning at home, and participating in TPQ events, are also indicators of success. This shows that there is effective communication between TPQ and students' families (Mas'ud, 2021).
4. **Management and Resource Management:** Success in managing TPQ can also be measured by how the institution manages its financial resources. Transparent and efficient fund management, with

appropriate allocation for educational needs, is an important indicator. Financial management (Drakic-Grgur, 2020) emphasized, "Good financial management reflects efficient management and is the key to the sustainability of non-formal education institutions such as TPQ." The availability of adequate facilities, such as comfortable classrooms, Al-Qur'an books, and teaching aids, as well as good maintenance of these facilities, are also indicators of success in managing TPQ. Good facilities show that this institution can provide a conducive learning environment (Drakic-Grgur, 2020).

5. **Long-Term Impact on Students:** The most basic indicator of TPQ success is changes in student behavior and character. According to Muhammad Quraish Shihab, a leading Muslim scholar, "The main aim of Islamic education, including at TPQ, is to form good morals. The success of TPQ can be seen from how the Islamic values taught are applied in the student's daily lives." The success of TPQ can also be seen in how many of its graduates continue their Islamic education at a higher level or are actively involved in religious activities in society. This shows that TPQ has instilled solid spiritual values and equipped students with the knowledge and enthusiasm to continue learning (Furqan & Hikmawan, 2021).
6. **Innovation and Program Development:** Another indicator of success is the innovation in the educational programs TPQ offers. If TPQ continues to develop new programs that suit the needs of society and students, the institution will be adaptive and oriented toward long-term development. In this digital era, TPQ's ability to utilize technology in teaching, such as using Al-Qur'an learning applications or online platforms to support learning, is an essential indicator of success.

The success of TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village in Maluku Tengah Regency can be measured through various indicators, which include teaching quality, student growth and engagement, community support, resource management, long-term impact on students, and innovation in program development. Experts' views show that success is not only seen from one aspect but from a combination of various factors that demonstrate an institution's ability to provide quality, relevant education and positively impact the community it serves.

Utilization of Local Resources

The Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village Qur'an Education Park (TPQ) leaders in Maluku Tengah Regency have demonstrated an extraordinary ability to utilize local resources to develop their institutions despite being in a disadvantaged area with limited infrastructure and funds. The following is a detailed explanation of how TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village leaders utilize local

resources, accompanied by the views of experts in educational management and leadership.

1. **Utilization of Local Human Resources:** TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village leaders actively involve local religious figures and the local community as teachers and support staff. This is done by recruiting ustadz and ustadzah who deeply understand the Koran and local Islamic traditions. By involving local human resources, TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village not only saves costs but also ensures that the education provided is relevant to the cultural and social context of the Maluku Tengah Regency community. According to Billah & Karim, in his book *Implementation of Total Quality Management in Education*, the involvement of local communities in education management is one of the keys to the success of educational institutions in disadvantaged areas. By utilizing local potential, academic institutions can develop curricula and teaching methods that suit local needs and conditions (Billah & Karim, 2021).
2. **Utilization of Local Facilities and Infrastructure:** Amid limited facilities, TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village leaders strive to empower available local infrastructure. For example, temporary study rooms are borrowed from mosques or empty residents' houses so that teaching can be carried out without requiring significant investments in physical construction. In addition, learning activities are held in places that are easily accessible to students, thereby reducing geographical barriers. In *Leading together: developing teacher leadership*, Eckert (2022) state that innovative leaders seek creative solutions in utilizing existing resources. This approach is essential in education in underdeveloped areas to overcome infrastructure constraints and ensure that the teaching and learning process can continue (Eckert, 2022).
3. **Collaboration with Local Communities:** TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village leaders have also succeeded in building close relationships with local communities who voluntarily support TPQ activities. For example, local communities often cooperate to improve TPQ facilities, donate teaching materials, or help organize significant events such as graduations and Al-Qur'an memorization competitions. This community involvement provides material support and strengthens the community's sense of belonging to TPQ. According to Fullan (2002), in *Leading in a Culture of Change*, leaders' success in involving local communities shows their ability to build strong social networks. This network provides additional support for educational institutions and creates profitable synergies between institutions and communities (Fullan, 2002).

4. **Use of Local Wisdom in Teaching:** Apart from utilizing local human resources and infrastructure, TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village leaders also incorporate elements of local wisdom in teaching. For example, the teaching methods are often adapted to traditional methods already known to the community, such as using traditional songs to memorize the Koran. This makes learning more relatable to students and relevant to their daily lives. Studies by Bourdieu in *The Logic of Practice* show that teaching rooted in local wisdom is more effective in facilitating learning because it is more relevant to students' cultural context. This allows students to understand and internalize the material being taught more efficiently (Jain, 2015).
5. **Local Economic Empowerment:** TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village leaders also support the local economy by utilizing products and services from local communities. For example, the books and stationery used by TPQ are purchased from small shops around the area, while food for TPQ events is often ordered from local homemakers. This supports local economic sustainability and strengthens relations between TPQ and the surrounding community. According to Hopkins (2005), in *Why can't Every School be a Great School*, local economic empowerment through education is one way to create a positive cycle between education and economic development in underdeveloped areas. Educational institutions can build closer community relationships and ensure ongoing support by supporting local economies (Hopkins, 2005).

The leader of TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village has demonstrated extraordinary abilities in utilizing various local resources, both in terms of people, infrastructure, local wisdom, and the economy. With this approach, they overcame multiple existing limitations and built strong relationships with local communities, strengthening the success and sustainability of the TPQ. This approach aligns with the views of experts who emphasize the importance of local involvement and empowerment in education management, especially in underdeveloped areas. With these strategies, TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village leaders optimally utilized local resources to support the institution's sustainability and development. This inclusive and community-based approach strengthens TPQ's position in society and ensures that the Al-Qur'an education provided remains relevant and of high quality, even in resource-limited areas such as Maluku Tengah Regency.

Strategy for Overcoming Challenges

Effective leadership plays a vital role in overcoming the various challenges Qur'an Education Parks (TPQ) faces in underdeveloped areas such as Maluku Tengah Regency.

These challenges include limited resources, inadequate infrastructure, and low community participation.

Influential leaders can maximize the use of available resources. For example, despite the limited budget, they can allocate funds wisely for priority needs such as purchasing Al-Qur'an books, teaching materials, and teacher welfare (Akhyar et al., 2021; Lavrenteva & Orland-Barak, 2023; Murwaningsih & Fauziah, 2023; Nuryadi et al., 2023).

1. **Fundraising:** Good leadership also involves seeking additional sources of funds. Leaders can take the initiative to raise funds through community donations, collaboration with donor agencies, or submitting aid proposals to the government and non-government organizations.
2. **Human Resource Development:** With limited funds, leaders can focus on developing the capacity of teachers and staff through internal training or collaboration with other educational institutions so that the quality of teaching is maintained even though material resources are limited.
3. **Overcoming Infrastructure Limitations: Utilization of Technology:** Effective leaders can utilize simple technology to support the teaching and learning process where physical infrastructure, such as adequate buildings, may not be available. For example, they are online learning applications that can complement face-to-face teaching.
4. **Empowerment of Local Facilities:** Smart leadership can also empower existing facilities, such as using community rooms or places of worship as temporary places to study. Leaders can also collaborate with the community to improve existing facilities.
5. **Initiative Innovative:** Creative leaders may develop innovative solutions such as classes or open-air learning to overcome classroom limitations.
6. **Increasing Teacher Competency:** Effective leaders focus on increasing teacher competency through ongoing training, workshops, and shared learning. They ensure that teachers not only master the Koranic material but also teach effective and exciting methods for children.
7. **Evaluation and Feedback:** Effective leadership involves a mechanism for regularly evaluating the teaching and learning process and taking corrective action based on feedback from teachers, students, and parents.
8. **Building Strong Relationships with the Community:** Effective leaders build strong relationships with the community through open and transparent communication. They involve religious and community leaders in the decision-making and management of TPQ, fostering a sense of shared ownership and responsibility.

9. **Socialization and Education:** Good leadership also involves active efforts to socialize the importance of Al-Qur'an education to the community, for example, through religious activities, parent meetings, and outreach programs in mosques or other public places.
10. **Parent Participation:** Effective leaders encourage parents' active participation in the educational process, for example, through regular meetings, supervision of home learning, and involvement in TPQ activities such as graduation events or competitions.

With these strategies, effective leadership not only overcomes existing challenges but also creates a conducive environment for quality Al-Qur'an learning and increases community support and involvement in the development of TPQ.

IV. CONCLUSION

Effective leadership at the Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village Qur'an Education Park (TPQ) in Maluku Tengah Regency plays a central role in achieving the success of this institution. Through a participative leadership style, TPQ leaders succeeded in creating a collaborative and innovative work environment, which improved the quality of teaching and strengthened relationships with the local community. Using local resources, including human resources, infrastructure, and local wisdom, has shown how this institution can adapt to limitations and achieve its educational goals.

Improving the quality of education, active community participation, and the long-term impact on students are indicators of TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village 's success. The strategies implemented by TPQ leaders to overcome challenges, including fundraising, human resource development, and empowerment of local facilities, have proven that with a clear vision and inclusive leadership, even institutions in disadvantaged areas can achieve significant success.

Overall, TPQ Nurul Huda Kampung Mamokeng, Tulehu Village is a clear example of how community-based leadership and using local resources can create quality education and positively impact society, even when faced with various challenges. This success reflects the managerial abilities of TPQ leaders but also shows the importance of the active involvement of all parties in the educational process.

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